

Software as Oxygen for Artificial Intelligence to Enable Business Opportunities in the Marketplace: A Conceptual Study

N.V.L.N.Prasad

Research Scholar, Ph.D (Law-) Part time
CMR University, Bengaluru

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:.. Prasad, N. V. L. N. “Software as Oxygen for Artificial Intelligence to Enable Business Opportunities in the Marketplace: A Conceptual Study.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 163–166.

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404503>

Abstract

This paper deals with the role and status of Software as an enabler on using Artificial Intelligence in the lifecycle of emerging business opportunities in the marketplace. Currently, the business has identified revenue impetus in adopting Artificial Intelligence in the innovative Business Models in e-commerce platforms created by technologies such as Bitcoin, Cryptocurrency, Cyber Technology, Digital Solutions, Machine Learning tools like robots, drones, sensor machines have created new market mining in the high potential use of internet. However, there are certain concerns on its Maintenance, Security, Safety, Environmental impact and Legal implications. The use of Artificial Intelligence enabled by Software differs from sector to sector. For example, the tools used in Information Technology sector deals with data analytics and data mining on automating business-processing activities. Infrastructure sector deals with machine learning, building technologies, floating buildings, digital doors, CCTV, the automobile sector focus on driverless vehicles, the health sector to enable doctor assisted digital surgeries, educational sector imparting digital knowledge. The significance of study under this Paper is to identify basic concepts involved in use of Software in the Artificial Intelligence and its impact on the business community in the 21st Century. To specifically focus on few selected initiatives and policy undertaken by Government of India for Digital India and the economic rights of the stakeholders of Artificial Intelligence in the marketplace thereby exploring the economic wealth that can be attributable to Artificial Intelligence and its impact on economic development.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Bitcoin, Blockchain, Cryptocurrency, Cyber Space, Cyber Security, Digital Solution, Economic Rights, E-commerce, Internet, Innovation, Machine Learning, Software, Smart Factory.

Introduction

Intelligence in general sense is an attribution of natural person and sometimes identified in few animals like chimpanzees, elephants and African grey parrots on earth. Intelligence is understood in different ways in different contexts, one of the widely popular sense defines “intelligence” as the ability to acquire and apply knowledge and skills that comprise of analytics of various data points acquired or made available to the individual. This attribute is in high demand for individual due its capacity to facilitate in ease of conducting activities, making right decision and to provide workable solution

by saving time and effort to humankind for the society. The degree, magnitude and measurement of intelligence depends on the level of accuracy, impact level and percentage of human or other support interference. It is an ideal system to have hundred percent intelligence and oxymoron. This aspect can be evaluated at specific task level or multiple tasks i.e. both at micro and macro level of humans conducting their day-to-day activities. This paper seeks to focus on a particular enabler i.e. “Software”, its use in the enhancement of intelligence systems or i-systems or smart-systems or digital-systems in machines or devices or equipment manmade therefore are artificial by nature. In simple terms when intelligence is infused into manmade systems, the activities, features or functionalities can be referred to as artificial intelligence. It is interesting to study and the need of the hour to examine the role of software in artificial intelligence necessary particularly in the area of economic development and business improvement in the emerging markets and for providing new leads to the traditional business models to improve revenue targets and cause the effect of wealth creation.

India specifically is one of the top economies of the world today and has put in place various initiatives that needs to incorporate advantages and improvements that artificial intelligence so to achieve under the “Digital India” and continue to be highly competitive in the global market. One important initiative undertaken by Government of India is the implementation of Goods and Services tax law i.e. indirect taxes established with an information technology (“IT”) backbone as the Goods and Services Tax Network or GSTN to support business conduct their activities under transparency and accountability under the IT framework for its compliance.

Basic Concepts

Software

Software in simple terms is a set of instructions written by using a language (software language such as C., C++, Java, etc.) developed by programmer to perform predetermined activity or task. The advantage of software cannot be disregarded due to its high speed capabilities, handling enormous data or information and interoperability between various systems that operate on multiple platforms across the world. This impact has created distanceless, timeless, placeness, personless in conducting activities. Historically, we can recollect the traditional television, an audio-video equipment was having many manual functionalities for its operation. By the introduction of new technologies and artificial intelligence solutions, today many features of operating the television are either sensor enabled or remote operated thereby physical interference of human beings for triggering its activities for automatically switch on or off, control sound, control colour, change the channels, etc.. Likewise, the use new technologies by incorporating artificial in intelligence today in various other sectors like automobiles (automatic start and off, touch sensor triggers to prevent accidents, etc.), building technologies (digital doors, remote controlling of various utilities in household activities like automatic switch on/off lights, burglar alarm, etc.), in entertainment sector, we can observe that there is use of drones, computer interface graphics and robots to support making of cinema to make look like real actors. Therefore, it is quite clear and obvious that Software today has been identified as separate sector, industry, market size, communication, banking, financial transactions, e-governance, day-to-day activities. Software is also necessary and integrated with other sectors due to the advantages offered by software.

Software as Enabler: “Code” as the cause and effect

One of the disruptive innovation caused in human history is the invention of television in the area of communications. Now, due to advanced science, the use of Smart Phone such as Apple or Samsung have miniature various independent devices into a simple user-friendly handheld device.

Some of the devices a Smart Phone comprises include camera (both snap shot & recorder), radio, television, videos, phone book, calendar, data or information cabinet/folders, arranging conference calls between people situated at difference places, etc., by implementation of the SMAC effect (i.e. Social media, Mobility, Analytics and Cloud Computing) created by use of STEM (i.e. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics).

Second to none is another invention i.e. internet (as interconnected network) & World Wide Web (as internet services) have created world ever imagined platform to the society; it has created innovative business models by presenting borderless world and converting the world into a global village. All these solutions were possible only by the use of “software”. New forms of business models evolved and new markets were recognised by the economic stakeholders due to introduction of internet related technologies like electronic mail for the purpose of obtaining commercial orders, obtaining payments by analytical and predictive solutions.

Block Chain, Bitcoin & Cryptocurrency: New ideas

Block Chain is a digital ledger-growing list of records called as blocks that comprises of transactions for e.g. bitcoin, digital currencies or any other cryptocurrency recorded in chronologically manner, decentralised and can be made public. The ledger allows writing but cannot be editing, adjusting or modified. This technology is yet to get legal recognition due security issues and awareness for the common user.

Challenges, Suggestions & Conclusion: Natural Intelligence v Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence emerging by way of Machine Learning techniques will not be able to completely replace the Natural Intelligence as there are restricted capabilities of devices to trigger functionalities like certain faculties like sentiments, relationships and emotions (e.g. happiness, anger, crying, etc.). This is an area of new research and future technologies, certain Gaming Software have been able to show some clues on touching these finer aspects of human creativity and imagination of virtual reality, but there is larger undone research in this area. It is evident that the business community has opportunity to exploit the benefits offered by introduction of software applications and networks. In parallel, it also brings the challenges of attaining accuracy in data or information, environmental concerns by causing pollution by generating electronic waste, cyber security threats and security breach incidents, continuing costs associated with the maintenance of Artificial Maintenance systems. Therefore, adequate legal regime by way of implementing privacy and data protection laws, use of environmentally safe systems by use of standards set as per the legal metrology law and bureau of Indian standards and implement internally recognised standards for information security such as ISO 270001 is necessary an certain important strategy aspects indicated by NITI Aayog.

It is necessary considering the size of data increasing globally is unimaginable and practically not possible for human to analyse, examine and understand them. Artificial Intelligence deals with the Machine Learning aspects include concepts such as fussy logic, pattern and trend analysis, smart statistics, cognitive informatics; Smart Factory (i.e. Industry 4.0) Deep Learning for Big data, Internet of Things if developed by right protocol and standards to provide the right solution. To conclude, we may note that Artificial Intelligence is a boon to society and business community if the modern and latest innovative technology is used in the right spirit with social responsibility towards the society and economic growth and development.

References

- European Commission, “The Age of Artificial Intelligence: Towards a European Strategy for Human-Centric Machines, European Political Strategy Center, Issue 29, 27 March, 2018. https://ec.europa.eu/epsc/sites/epsc/files/epsc_strategicnote_ai.pdf Visited Aug 15, 2018) and refer the Leaflet, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Applications ISSN 0975-900X (Online) (this website provides for various interesting topics of interest pertaining to Artificial Intelligence) Source: http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijaia/ijaia_leaflet.pdf visited date Aug 15, 2018)
- Refer the Discussion Paper by NITI Aayog, “National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence # AIFORALL”, June 2018.
- Suggest to refer, SA Oke, “A Literature Review on Artificial Intelligence”, International Journal of Information and Management Sciences, Vol 19 (4) pp.535-570, (2008)<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.471.814&rep=rep1&type=pdf> (Visited 15 Aug, 2018)
- Suggest to Refer, “Artificial Intelligence and Life in 2030: One Hundred Year Study on Artificial Intelligence, report of the 2015 Study Panel”, September, 2016 (Source: https://ai100.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/ai_100_report_0906fnlc_single.pdf Visited Aug 15, 2018) and reference can also be made to (Source: https://dspace.library.uvic.ca/bitstream/handle/1828/8314/Evans_Guy-Warwick_MSc_2017.pdf?sequence=1 Visited Aug 15, 2018)